
THE GEORGE
WASHINGTON
UNIVERSITY

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Military Spending

DATS 6103 - Tejaswini Vuppu

List Of Countries & Years

- USA
- China
- Russia
- Germany
- UK
- Italy
- Iran
- Israel
- Saudi Arabia
- France

2011 to 2017

Goals

- Compare the military data to that country's GDP.
- Compare the overall military spending of all the 10 countries in absolute and percentages.
- Compare the per person military spending with the per person GDP.
- Single out the fastest growing countries in military spending in absolute and percentages.

Source Of Data

- Military spending data is taken from Stockholm International Peace research institute's.
- GDP data is taken from World Bank (Links are provided in jupyter notebook)

Military Data vs Country's GDP

- GDP is highest for the USA and also grows for China, which follows the same way. But the rest all other countries are pretty stable on their GDP's.

Percentage spending military vs GDP

Military Data vs Country's GDP(continuation)

- Saudi Arabia has the highest percentage of military spending versus GDP even though the USA has the highest GDP.
- We noticed that Saudi Arabia stays top with 28.0% in military expenses.
- Rest two places are handled by Israel with 16.1 %, succeeded by the Russian Federation of 12.3%.
- Being highest in GDP, United states is spending much less on military spending with 10.6%.

Compare the overall military spending of all countries

- USA is highest in military spending which is 55.6% and Iran being the lowest with 1.0%.
- USA is expensing more than all countries spending.

Military Spending by Year

- We can see that USA used to spend more than 7 million dollars in 2011, It's getting decreased to closely 6 million dollars.

- China is in the 2nd place spending on military and its gradually increasing its spending limits.

Closer Look

- As we see USA is spending more than half of all other countries are spending, It's always good to have a closer look on how the small countries are spending.
- When you see closer look without USA and China we can see that Saudi Arabia is approximately spent 1 million in 2014-2015 period.

Overall military spending of all countries

- With the military spending data in percentage, we can conclude that USA is spending around 50 to 60 percent on overall contribution.

Per Person Military spending vs Per Person GDP

- We can calculate the per-person military spending with dividing the population with military spending of the country(military spending per cap).
- In the same way we can also calculate the per-person GDP and it can be also called as GDP per cap.
- We can calculate the ratios of both to get the percentages of per-person military vs per-person GDP.

per-person military and per-person GDP %

- We can clearly see that Saudi Arabia is doing great job on per person military and per person GDP percentage.

Military spending Per Person to the Per persons GDP percentage

Bar plot per-person MLT vs GDP

Military spending Per Person of 10 countries to Per Person GDP

Fastest Growing Countries in Military Spending

- Below graph represent the closer look of countries without USA and China, In there we can see Saudi Arabia is rapidly growing from 2011 to 2015. Which makes Saudi Arabia can be considered as a fastest growing country.

Fastest Growing Countries percentage

Conclusion

- USA has highest military spending and GDP.
- Saudi Arabia has highest military spending as percentage of GDP.
- Fastest growing country can be China as well Saudi Arabia based on closer look.

References

- <https://data.worldbank.org/>
- <https://sipri.org/databases/milex>
- <https://www.kaggle.com/>